

Studies on some *N*-Acyl *N*-Phenylhydroxylamines as Metal-Complexing Ligands. Part VIII. Dissociation Constants of some *N*-Hydroxysuccinamic Acids

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Acid dissociation constants of a number of *N*-hydroxysuccinamic acids e. g. *N*-phenyl (R_pH_2), *N*-*o*-tolyl ($R_t^oH_2$) and *N*-*m*-tolyl ($R_t^mH_2$), have been determined potentiometrically at a constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.5$). Same values are obtained with respect to the first dissociation constants (k_1^*) in each case. Regarding the second dissociation constants (k_2^*), acidic characteristics found are in the order $R_t^oH^- > R_pH^- > R_t^mH^-$.

In earlier communications^{1,2} the synthesis of *N*-phenyl *N*-hydroxysuccinamic acid (R_pH_2) and *N*-*o*-tolyl-*N*-hydroxysuccinamic acid ($R_t^oH_2$) and some of their metal complexes have been reported. Recently *N*-*m*-tolyl *N*-hydroxysuccinamic acid ($R_t^mH_2$) has been synthesised³. In the present investigation dissociation constants of the *N*-hydroxysuccinamic acids in aqueous solution have been determined following Calvin-Wilson pH-titration technique⁴, as the knowledge of the dissociation constants is essential in the determination of stability constants of their metal chelates.

Experimental

All chemicals used were either of A. R. quality or properly purified. Experimental procedure consists of potentiometric titration 0.01M ligand solution containing known amount of $HClO_4$ (0.01M) in aqueous solution with a standard solution of NaOH (0.1M) at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$. The ionic strength of the medium was kept constant ($\mu=0.50$) by adding requisite amount of $NaClO_4$.

With a Cambridge pH-meter (Portable type), pH-measurements were made. Electrode systems consisted of a glass electrode of 1-13 pH range in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell by means of an agar 2M sodium nitrate bridge

In order to determine the final acid concentration a graphical method⁵ was employed. For this purpose pH values of a number of $HClO_4$ solutions of known strength in aqueous solution, having same ionic strength ($\mu=0.5$) were noted and pH values were plotted against negative logarithm of the acid concentrations. The final acid concentrations were extrapolated from the corresponding pH values. The values of \bar{n}_H [average number of proton bound to the ligand ions (R_p)²⁻ or (R_t^o)²⁻ or (R_t^m)²⁻] were calculated following equation (6) and plotted against pH.

Results and Discussion

In aqueous solution the stepwise acid dissociation of ligands RH_2 may be represented as :

$$\text{Therefore } k_2^* = \frac{[RH^-][H^+]}{[RH_2]} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$\text{and } k_1^* = \frac{[R^{2-}][H^+]}{[RH^-]} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

$$\text{By definition, } \bar{n}_H = \frac{2[RH_2] + [RH^-]}{R} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Where R=total concentration of the ligand.

At any stage of titration after attainment of equilibrium,

$$R = RH_2 + RH^- + R^{2-} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

$$\text{and } P + H^+ = F + OH^- + [RH^-] + 2[R^{2-}] \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

where F and P represent the initial concentrations of free acid and amount of alkali, and H^+ and OH^- are the concentrations of acid and alkali after the attainment of equilibrium.

$$\text{From (3), (4), (5) } \bar{n}_H = \frac{2R - (P + H^+ - F - OH^-)}{R} \\ = 2 - \frac{(P + H^+ - F - OH^-)}{R} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

One may deduce the equation (7) from the relation (3)

$$(\bar{n}_H - 2) \frac{[H^+]^2}{k_1^* k_2^*} + (\bar{n}_H - 1) \frac{[H^+]}{k_1^*} + \bar{n}_H = 0 \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

So when $\bar{n}_H = 0.5$

$$3[H^+]^2_{\bar{n}_H=0.5} + k_2^*[H^+]_{\bar{n}_H=0.5} - k_1^*k_2^* = 0 \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

and when $\bar{n}_H = 1.5$

$$[H^+]^2_{\bar{n}_H=1.5} - k_2^*[H^+]_{\bar{n}_H=1.5} - 3k_1^*k_2^* = 0 \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

The acid dissociation constants have been evaluated from the \bar{n}_H against pH curves following Bjerrum's half- \bar{n} method⁶. These values are then refined employing equations (8) and (9). However after refinement the values obtained are practically the same as found by Bjerrum's half- \bar{n} method. Results are stated in Table-1.

Standard deviations (σ) have been calculated⁷ using relation (10)

$$(\sigma) = \pm \left[\frac{\sum (\Delta \bar{n})^2}{N} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

where $\bar{n} = \bar{n}_H$ (calc.) \sim \bar{n}_H (expt.) and N = number of observations. The \bar{n}_H (calc.) values have been obtained from equation (11)

$$\bar{n}_H(\text{calc.}) = \frac{2[\text{H}^+]^2 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_1^*k_2^*}}{1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_1^*} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{k_1^*k_2^*}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

using the experimental values of pH and the determined values of pk_2^* and pk_1^* . Limits of error have been evaluated from the horizontal deviation of the two curves—the experimental plot of \bar{n}_H against pH and the calculated one obtained on plotting \bar{n}_H (calc.) against experimental pH . Results are stated in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF *N*-HYDROXY : SUCCINAMIC ACIDS

$t = 30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$

Species	R_pH_2	$R_t^{\circ}H_2$	$R_t^mH_2$
pk_2^*	4.32 ± 0.02	4.32 ± 0.04	4.32 ± 0.04
pk_1^*	8.64 ± 0.04	8.56 ± 0.04	8.80 ± 0.04

Standard deviations (σ) have been found to be ± 0.003 ($0 < \bar{n}_H < 2.0$), ± 0.012 ($0 < n_H < 2.0$) and ± 0.013 ($0.4 < \bar{n}_H < 2.0$) in the cases of R_pH_2 , $R_t^{\circ}H_2$ respectively. The deviation is very slight with respect to R_pH_2 and $R_t^{\circ}H_2$ but is much greater in the case of $R_t^mH_2$ at higher pH values i.e. when \bar{n}_H is less than 0.4. This may be attributed to decomposition of the ligand at higher pH values.

Constancy of pk_2^* values in the series of ligands (Table 1) indicates that the ionization of $-COOH$ group

is unaffected by any sorts of substitution in the benzene ring. This is due to interposition of two methylene units in between $-COOH$ group and rest of the molecule. However the pk_1^* values suggest that the environment of the $-N(OH)-CO-$ hydrogen is slightly changed as a result of substitution in the benzene ring. The trend of variation in acidic characteristic as obtained in the present investigation may be stated in the ligand order $R_t^{\circ}H^- > R_pH^- > R_t^mH^-$.

Methyl group in meta-position in the *m*-tolylsuccinamic acid derivative ($R_t^mH^-$), exerts an inductive effect ($+I$) and lowers the acid strength from that of the phenylsuccinamate anion (R_pH^-). On the other hand in *o*-tolylsuccinamic acid anion ($R_t^{\circ}H^-$), the methyl group in the ortho-position exerts a small ($+I$) effect and a larger steric effect; the latter causes the $N-O-H$ system to move out of the plane of the benzene ring and the acid-weakening resonance effect is greatly diminished⁸, consequently $R_t^{\circ}H^-$ behaves as stronger acid than R_pH^- .

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